

LEADING THE WAY THROUGH CHANGE: A STUDY OF TRANSITION OF LEADERSHIP IN IMMACULATE CONCEPTION COLLEGE OF BALAYAN INC.

Krishna Nicole L. Genebla¹, Niel Randle M. Comia², Reynan C. Hernandez³, Kean Ivan V. Ople⁴, Jazmin Claire O. Mallari⁵, Jowenie A. Mangarin⁶

¹²³⁴⁵⁶ Immaculate Conception College of Balayan, Inc., Plaza Mabini, 4213, Balayan, Batangas, Philippines

Corresponding Emails: mail@iccbalayan.edu.ph

Available Online: February 2024
 Revised: January 2024
 Accepted: December 2024
 Received: January 2024

Volume 2 Issue 4 (2024)
 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10785269
 E-ISSN: 2984-7184
 P-ISSN: 2984-7176
<https://getinternational.org/research/>

Abstract

This research explores the crucial role of leadership transitions in educational institutions, particularly at Immaculate Conception College of Balayan, Inc. (ICCB). Recognizing the profound impact of leadership practices on organizational effectiveness, this study addresses nuanced aspects of employee engagement during transitions. Using a qualitative case study design involving face-to-face interviews, common themes emerge regarding the transition of leadership, such as inclusive decision-making, resistance to new policies, unclear communication, continuity in vision, mission, and commitment, and transparency. The findings underscore the substantial influence of leadership transitions on the institution's dynamics, shaping its mission, vision, and commitment to both students and employees. Proactively addressing challenges is emphasized as crucial for maintaining a positive work environment and enhancing organizational effectiveness. The study further recommends a strategic focus on transforming challenges into opportunities, prioritizing employee engagement, and implementing the outlined strategies to foster a healthy work-life relationship within Immaculate Conception College of Balayan, Inc.

Keywords: *Leadership, Transitions, ICCBI, Work-life balance, Challenges, Opportunities*

Recommended Citation:

Genebla, K. N., Comia, N. R., Hernandez, R., Ople, K. I., Mallari, J. C., Mangarin, J. (2024). LEADING THE WAY THROUGH CHANGE: A STUDY OF TRANSITION OF LEADERSHIP IN IMMACULATE CONCEPTION COLLEGE OF BALAYAN INC., GUILD OF EDUCATORS IN TESOL INTERNATIONAL RESEARCH JOURNAL, 2(4), 1-22. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10785269>

Introduction

In the dynamic landscape of educational institutions, adapting to the impact of leadership changes parallels the swift transformations inherent in the field of education. Leadership transitions play a pivotal role in shaping the trajectory of progress and success within an institution, as exemplified by the recent transition of administration at Immaculate Conception College of Balayan Inc. (ICCB). ICCBI, renowned for its commitment to academic excellence and holistic student development, underwent a shift from its previous leadership to a new administration. This transition reflects the school's dedication to managing change while upholding its mission and vision, with a primary focus on ensuring the continuous success of its students.

The influence of leadership on employee sentiments and organizational success is widely acknowledged, with effective leadership styles correlating with heightened employee satisfaction (Mangarin, 2023). In the corporate realm, leadership profoundly shapes an organization's culture and reputation, making the performance of both employees and leaders crucial for success. Amidst a leadership transition, the credibility of the incoming leader becomes paramount, necessitating adept communication of their vision, proficient decision-making, and transparent engagement with their followers. Notably, the subjective nature of leadership introduces varied perceptions of effectiveness, complicating transitions, especially in cases where a predecessor has been intentionally removed.

Building on a rich literature on leadership transitions in corporate organizations, including studies by Herawaty et al. (2020) and James (2020), which underscore the critical importance of an expedited transition process and strategic onboarding for enhancing leadership effectiveness. Herawaty et al. (2020) emphasize the need for a well-structured and swift transition process, recognizing that a prolonged or disorganized transition can lead to uncertainties and potential disruptions within an organization. A carefully planned and efficiently executed transition is essential for maintaining organizational stability, employee morale, and overall effectiveness. This is particularly relevant in the corporate setting, where quick adaptation to new leadership is crucial for maintaining productivity and ensuring smooth continuity of operations.

Moreover, James (2020) highlights the significance of strategic onboarding during leadership transitions. Effective onboarding is seen as a crucial element in helping leaders integrate seamlessly into their new roles. The study likely explores how a well-designed onboarding process, encompassing orientation, mentorship, and clear communication, can positively impact a leader's ability to understand the organizational culture, build relationships with team members, and align with the company's goals and values. Strategic onboarding is essential for accelerating the leader's effectiveness and minimizing any potential disruption caused by the transition.

Furthermore, Kaul et al. (2022) shed light on strategies for navigating challenges during the onboarding process, emphasizing the pivotal role of onboarding in facilitating the successful integration of leaders into organizational contexts. This study likely delves into specific challenges that leaders may face during the onboarding phase and offers practical strategies to overcome these challenges. Effective onboarding, as highlighted by Kaul et al., goes beyond mere orientation; it involves creating an environment that fosters understanding, collaboration, and a sense of belonging, ultimately contributing to a leader's successful integration into the organizational fabric.

Pedroso et al. (2021) offer a fresh perspective on leadership transitions by underscoring the significance of thoughtful planning and support during critical transition periods. This study likely explores the broader context of leadership transitions, considering the multifaceted challenges that may arise and emphasizing the need for proactive planning and robust support mechanisms. The research may delve into the role of organizational culture, communication strategies, and the human aspect of leadership transitions, providing nuanced insights into how thoughtful planning can mitigate potential disruptions and contribute to a smoother transition.

However, despite these insights from corporate literature, a notable gap exists in understanding such transitions within educational institutions like schools. Within educational institutions, school administrators play a pivotal role in influencing school administration and impacting the learning environment and the success of both students and teachers (Kiral and Basaran, 2018). Navigating the challenges of a leadership transition requires principals

to prioritize the best interests of the school community, recognizing both the opportunities and challenges inherent in such transitions.

With that, this study seeks to bridge this gap by examining the transition between the old and new leadership at ICCBI and shedding light on the effects on leadership, management, and supervision within the educational context. The appointment of the new administrators of ICCBI has catalyzed shifts in leadership, management, and supervision practices, prompting keen observation from employees and students alike. By delving into the intricacies of the transition, the study contributes valuable insights for navigating leadership changes in educational institutions, with the overarching goal of assisting ICCBI in seamlessly upholding its mission, vision, and commitment to student success. The findings and recommendations also aspire to offer guidance to other educational institutions undergoing similar leadership transitions.

Statement of the Problem

This study seeks to understand the effects of the transition of administration to the new administration, specifically scrutinizing its effects on crucial aspects of the institution, including leadership, management, and supervision. The identified problems are articulated as follows:

1. How does the transition of leadership from the former administration to the new administration affect the overall leadership dynamics within Immaculate Conception College of Balayan, Inc.?
2. What are the challenges and opportunities that arise during this leadership transition period in terms of effectively managing and supervising in the institution's operations?
3. How does the leadership transition impact the institution's mission, vision, and commitment to the student success and employee's welfare?
4. How can these challenges be effectively addressed to maintain a positive work environment and enhance organizational effectiveness?
5. Based on the findings of the study, what strategic plan maybe proposed to the ICCBI administrators and other schools?

Methodology

The researchers employed a qualitative case study design to thoroughly investigate the leadership transition at ICCBI. This approach allows for in-depth exploration through interviews and observations, providing a holistic view of the transition's impact (Creswell, 2014). The study, conducted during the academic year 2023–2024, adopts a longitudinal perspective to capture the evolving dynamics of the institution. By specifically focusing on supervision, management, and leadership, the research aims to offer a comprehensive analysis of the organizational changes resulting from the transition. This method provides a nuanced understanding of the challenges and opportunities associated with leadership changes in ICCBI.

Population and Sampling

The researchers employed purposeful sampling, a deliberate non-probability technique wherein participants were selectively chosen based on specific criteria. For this study, 18 participants met the criterion of having a minimum of 5 years of experience at the school. This focused sampling strategy was designed to gather insights from individuals with substantial experience, ensuring a deep understanding of the nuances surrounding the educational institution's leadership changes (QuestionPro, 2023).

Instrumentations

The study used interview guide questions as the primary instrument to assess the impacts of the transition of administration at ICCBI. This approach facilitated in-depth conversations, ensuring accurate and insightful information collection. Using a semi-structured format with predetermined questions and flexibility for probing inquiries, participants freely expressed opinions and shared experiences, fostering an organic exchange of information. This approach

provided valuable insights into the challenges and adaptations during the leadership transition in educational institutions.

Data Collection

After securing permissions from the school administrators of ICCBI, the researchers conducted face-to-face interviews with the 18 participants (12 teachers and 6 staff). Over the course of two weeks, the researchers gathered rich insights into leadership transitions at ICCBI. Thematic analysis was then applied to distill key themes, providing a structured approach to understanding nuanced aspects of the educational institution's leadership transitions (Longe, 2023). Subsequently, a strategic plan was formulated to provide recommendations based on the findings.

Data Analysis

Researchers utilized thematic analysis to comprehensively explore the impact of the transition of administration. Following Streefkerk's (2022) guidance, interviews were transcribed into written text, ensuring accuracy for analysis. Coding was applied to organize qualitative data, bringing out underlying themes. Diverse analytical methods were used for interpretation, providing deeper insights. Verification processes were implemented to maintain data integrity and add rigor to the exploration. These collective methods contribute to a thorough and systematic examination, enhancing the reliability and robustness of the findings.

Ethical Considerations

To initiate the interviews, the researchers sought permission from the administrators of ICCBI. Upon approval, a request letter was sent to the chosen employees and staff, seeking their consent to participate in the study. Once consent was granted, the researchers coordinated with the participants to schedule the survey and interviews. During the interview, respondents were not required to include any identifying information, ensuring the confidentiality of their responses. Comments were kept anonymous to maintain the integrity of the research. To further protect confidentiality, participants were assigned code numbers or names, which were used consistently across all research documentation. Notes, interview transcripts, and any other potentially identifying data were securely stored. Participant data was treated confidentially unless there was a legal obligation to report it, ensuring privacy. The voluntary participation in this study was acknowledged and respected. The decision to partake in the study was entirely at their discretion. Participants were required to sign a consent form if they chose to be involved, and they had the freedom to state their reasons for participating or not. Withdrawal from the study did not impact any existing relationships between the researcher and the respondents. Additionally, participants were assured of receiving their data back from the study before the data collection concluded.

Results and Discussions

Presented below are the data analysis and findings from the interview conducted among the participants of the study, revealing important themes about the transition of administrations in ICCBI.

Table 1. Effects of the transition of leadership on the overall leadership dynamics within Immaculate Conception College of Balayan, Inc.

Major Themes	Excerpts
<p>Inclusive Decision-Making Process</p>	<p>"Yes, all the coordinators can share their idea, can give command but with the supervision of the head." (P1)</p> <p>"The new administration always seeks to help their employees and they ask for suggestions for the betterment of everyone." (P2)</p> <p>"Sometimes there is a need in shifting the decision-making process to create better results from our work." (P3)</p>

	<p>"There is better sense of unity as activities, effort was held to include all department non-teaching, maintenance (i.e., team building)." (P9)</p> <p>"As I know, the command is always caring from the highest down to its subordinates." (P11)</p> <p>"Still the same, the top-level administrator decides every major decision in the institution." (P12)</p> <p>"Yes, it has many differences in the process of decision-making." (P14)</p> <p>"As I said, there is a change specifically in the decision-making process, the chain of command, wherein the current administration willingly listens to the voices and suggestions of the employee." (P16)</p>
Employee Growth and Well-being	<p>"They help nurture the growth of all employees and help them to grow holistically." (P1)</p> <p>"A dynamic and successful transition of management results in a healthy environment among employees." (P2)</p> <p>"The current administration is so generous in terms of finding ways to help their workers on their professional needs." (P6)</p> <p>"With the new administration immediately after transition, the salary grade has been aligned, and the workload has been properly compensated." (P11)</p>
Enhanced Communication and Collaboration	<p>"Successful transition management involves communicating with the employees like monthly meetings and etc..." (P3)</p> <p>"There's a better sense of unity as activities and effort were held to include all departments, non-teaching, maintenance (i.e., team building)." (P9)</p> <p>"They continuously properly managing the institution." (P14)</p>
Increase in Salary and Compensation	<p>"Many employees had a chance to have a high salary and they are given to speak out." (P4)</p> <p>"With the new administration immediately after transition the salary grade has been aligned and the workload has been properly compensated..." (P11)</p>
New Leadership Styles	<p>"In my opinion, the new administration would like the transformational style of leadership." (P5)</p> <p>"The new administration is into development-centric compared to the previous one." (P12)</p> <p>"The most notable change in leadership style of this current administration is the priority and its goal." (P16)</p>
Equality and Inclusion	<p>"Yes, all the coordinators can share their idea, can give command but with the supervision of the head." (P1)</p> <p>"There is equality among their employees." (P8)</p> <p>"Ask I said there is a change specifically in the decision-making process, the chain of command, wherein the current administration willingly listens to the voices and suggestions of the employee." (P16)</p>

Table 1. illustrates the effects of the transition of leadership on the overall leadership dynamics within Immaculate Conception College of Balayan, Inc. There are six (6) major themes identified about the effects of transition of administration in leadership among employees:

1. Inclusive Decision-Making Processes
2. Employee Growth and Well-Being
3. Enhanced Communication and Collaboration
4. Increase Salary and Compensation
5. New Leadership Styles
6. Equality and Inclusion

Inclusive Decision-Making Process

The major theme of "Inclusive Decision-Making Process" emerges as a notable effect of the leadership transition within ICCBI. In organizational decision-making, particularly in educational institutions, actively involving frontline workers is deemed crucial. The study by Hillotin (2022) emphasizes that those directly engaged in the work not only play a key role in decision-making initiatives but also wield significant influence.

In fact, Participant 3 highlights the necessity of shifting the decision-making process to enhance the outcomes of their work. This sentiment is supported by Participant 14, who notes the existence of many differences in the decision-making process. Additionally, Participant 16 adds valuable insight, noting a change in the chain of command under the current administration. The noteworthy shift involves a willingness to listen to the voices and suggestions of employees, reflecting a more inclusive approach to decision-making.

This major theme suggests that the transition in leadership at ICCBI has brought about a positive transformation in the decision-making process, where the perspectives and input of employees are not only acknowledged but actively sought. This shift aligns with contemporary organizational paradigms that recognize the importance of inclusivity in decision-making for fostering a collaborative and effective work environment.

Employee Growth and Well-Being

This second major theme not only resonates deeply but also plays a pivotal role in shaping the trajectory of employee development and welfare within the organizational framework. It recognizes that leadership shifts extend beyond the surface-level adjustments in roles and responsibilities, penetrating into the very fabric of the work environment and its effect on the individuals who contribute to the organization. Leadership changes may influence the availability of learning opportunities, mentorship programs, and other developmental initiatives that contribute to the overall well-being of employees. Holman, Johnson, and O'Connor (2018) highlight the significance of not only valuing work contributions but also safeguarding the health and protection of individuals within workplace environments. This underscores the importance of considering the broader well-being of employees in the organizational context.

Participant 1 notes that the leadership transition helps nurture the growth of all employees, fostering holistic development. Participant 2 supports this by stating that a dynamic and successful transition of management results in a healthy environment among employees. Additionally, Participant 6 highlights the generosity of the current administration in finding ways to support workers with their professional needs.

This major theme reflects a positive correlation between effective leadership transitions and the holistic growth and well-being of employees. It suggests that a successful transition not only contributes to a healthy work environment but also demonstrates a commitment to addressing the professional needs and overall welfare of employees.

Enhanced Communication and Collaboration

The third theme emphasizes how leadership transitions act as catalysts, triggering and promoting improved communication channels and collaborative efforts within the organization. It explores the significant impact that changes in leadership can have on communication dynamics and collaboration among team members and different levels of the organization.

Spreitzer (2015) emphasizes that leaders who empower their team members contribute to a culture infused with trust and confidence. The act of granting autonomy signifies a deep trust in the skills and judgment of each team member, fostering an environment where individuals feel empowered and valued.

Participant 3 supports this theme by noting that successful transition management involves regular communication with employees through monthly meetings and other means. This proactive communication strategy is crucial for maintaining transparency and keeping employees informed during times of change. Participant 9 further reinforces the theme by highlighting a better sense of unity resulting from inclusive activities and efforts that involve all departments, including non-teaching and maintenance, through team-building initiatives.

In essence, the "Enhanced Communication and Collaboration" theme emphasizes that effective leadership transitions not only communicate trust and empowerment but also contribute to a more cohesive and unified organizational culture through improved communication strategies and collaborative initiatives.

Increase in Salary and Compensation

The fourth theme underscores the substantial impact that leadership transitions can have on the financial aspects of employees and is supported by Holman, Johnson, and O'Connor (2018), emphasizing the importance of recognizing the value of work and prioritizing the well-being of individuals within work environments. Holman et al. (2018) promote a holistic approach that not only values contributions but actively ensures the well-being and safety of every individual in the workplace, aligning with the idea that financial compensation is an integral part of acknowledging the value of employees.

Participant 4 provides a firsthand account, stating that many employees had the chance to experience a higher salary, and they were given the opportunity to voice their concerns. This suggests that the leadership transition positively influenced the salary structure and opened avenues for employees to actively participate in discussions related to compensation.

Participant 11 supports this theme by noting that, with the new administration, the salary grade was aligned and the workload was properly compensated immediately after the transition. This indicates a proactive approach by the new leadership to addressing compensation-related issues and ensuring that employees are fairly remunerated for their work.

This holistic perspective aligns with the concept that financial compensation plays a crucial role in acknowledging and valuing employees, emphasizing the interconnected nature of recognizing contributions and promoting the overall welfare of individuals within the organizational setting.

New Leadership Style

The fifth theme represents a transformative shift in leadership approaches following the transition, emphasizing the evolution and implementation of innovative methodologies. This implies a departure from traditional or conventional leadership styles, signaling a proactive embrace of novel and forward-thinking strategies. The theme suggests that leadership transitions serve as catalysts for change, encouraging leaders to explore and implement innovative approaches to address challenges and foster organizational growth. The evolution in leadership methodologies underscores a commitment to adaptability, continuous improvement, and a willingness to explore new avenues for achieving organizational objectives.

A well-defined organizational structure, outlining reporting relationships, responsibilities, and authority levels, contributes significantly to an administration's success (Robbins and Coulter, 2019). The clarity provided by such a structure fosters efficiency, streamlines decision-making processes, and establishes a framework for effective operations.

Participant 5 expresses the opinion that the new administration is inclined towards a transformational style of leadership. This indicates a departure from conventional leadership styles, suggesting a focus on inspiring and motivating employees towards a shared vision of growth and development.

Participant 12 supports this theme by highlighting that the new administration is development-centric compared to the previous one. This emphasizes a commitment to fostering growth and improvement, aligning with the principles of transformational leadership.

Participant 16 adds to this narrative by pointing out that the most notable change in the leadership style of the current administration is its priority and its goal. This implies that the leadership transition has brought about a shift in focus and objectives, potentially aligning with a more modern and strategic approach to leadership.

This underscores the transformative nature of leadership following the transition, with a shift towards innovative and development-centric methodologies. This aligns with established principles that emphasize the importance of a clearly defined organizational structure for successful administrations.

Equality and inclusion

The last theme stands out as a noteworthy consequence arising from the transition of leadership, signifying a substantial influence on the overall landscape of leadership dynamics. This theme delves into the transformative effects that leadership transitions can have on fostering an environment of equality and inclusion within the organization. It encompasses the reshaping of policies, practices, and organizational culture to ensure fair treatment, equal opportunities, and the active involvement of diverse perspectives. The transition serves as a catalyst for promoting an inclusive workplace where individuals, regardless of their background, feel valued, respected, and fully integrated into the organizational fabric. This theme underscores the leadership's role in championing diversity and fostering an inclusive culture, reflecting a commitment to creating a workplace that embraces and celebrates individual differences.

Participant 8 notes that there is equality among employees under the new administration. This implies a commitment to fostering a workplace culture that prioritizes equal opportunities, fair treatment, and inclusion for all employees.

Participant 1 supports this notion by mentioning that all coordinators can share their ideas and give commands, albeit under the supervision of the head. This suggests a collaborative and inclusive decision-making process that involves input from various levels, promoting equality in the exchange of ideas.

Participant 16 further reinforces the theme by highlighting a change in the decision-making process and the chain of command. The current administration, according to P16, willingly listens to the voices and suggestions of the employees. This indicates a departure from a more hierarchical and authoritative structure, fostering a culture of inclusivity and openness to diverse perspectives.

This theme underscores the positive impact of leadership transition on fostering a workplace environment characterized by equal opportunities, collaborative decision-making, and a commitment to listening to the voices and suggestions of all employees. This aligns with the broader goal of creating a more inclusive and equitable organizational culture.

Table 2. Challenges that arise during the leadership transition period in terms of effectively managing and supervising the ICCBI operations

Major Themes	Excerpts
Resistance to New Policies	"Faculty and staff may resist new policies, roles, and procedures; unclear communication, decision about budget allocation and resource distribution make change with the new leadership which can lead to concern about findings for program department." (P12)
Attachment to Previous Leaders	"The challenge was the adjustment for the employees because they became attached to the previous leaders." (P9)
Communication Challenges	"Connection challenge the communication by school administrators." (P16) "...unclear communication and uncertainties, which can lead to concern about findings for program department." (P12) "The implementation of new policies or strategies that are unfamiliar to the members of the institution." (P1)

Table 2. stresses the challenges that arise during the leadership transition period in terms of effectively managing and supervising the ICCBI operations. There are three major themes that emerge as significant challenges in management, and those are:

1. Resistance to New Policies
2. Attachment to Previous Leaders
3. Communication Challenges

Resistance to New Policies

The major theme of 'Resistance to New Policies' emerges as one of the prominent challenges during leadership transitions, posing significant obstacles to the effective management and supervision of the transition period. This theme encapsulates the difficulties encountered when introducing new policies or communicating changes inadequately, leading to resistance and potential disruptions within the organizational framework. It sheds light on the complexities associated with navigating a transition phase, where unclear communication and resistance to policy changes can impede the smooth progression of leadership initiatives.

Participant 12 expresses concerns about potential resistance from faculty and staff to new policies, roles, and procedures. This resistance, according to P12, may stem from unclear communication, decisions about budget allocation, and resource distribution associated with the new leadership. This highlights the critical role of clear and transparent communication in mitigating resistance to change during leadership transitions.

The theme aligns with findings from a study conducted by Akan and Betül (2016), emphasizing the importance of keeping employees well-informed about organizational change processes and seeking their opinions regarding decisions. This inclusive approach helps break resistance to change by fostering understanding and collaboration. Addressing this theme is crucial for ensuring a seamless transition that minimizes resistance, enhances clarity, and fosters a conducive environment for effective management and supervision.

Attachment to Previous Leaders

The identification of the second major theme explores the relationship between lingering sentiments toward past leaders and the difficulties associated with accepting new leadership paradigms. It emphasizes the interplay of organizational culture, individual loyalties, and the inherent challenges involved in navigating a redefined leadership landscape.

Participant 9 articulates the challenges associated with this theme by stating, "The challenge was the adjustment for the employees because they became attached to the previous leaders." This statement underscores the emotional and psychological aspect of attachment to previous leaders, posing a challenge during the transition to new leadership.

The theme highlights the complexities involved in managing organizational change, where employees may harbor attachments to leaders from the past. Such attachments can influence their perceptions, reactions, and overall adaptation to the new leadership structure.

In essence, this theme highlights the complex nature of organizational transitions, where emotional ties to past leaders can present hurdles in embracing and adapting to a new leadership era. Recognizing and addressing these emotional connections becomes crucial to fostering a smoother transition process.

Communication Challenges

The theme of "Communication Challenges" underscores the significant hurdles faced in maintaining effective communication during leadership transitions. This theme, supported by the statement from P16, "Connection challenges communication by school administrators," points to the difficulties experienced in establishing clear and consistent communication channels under new leadership. The statement suggests that challenges in connectivity pose obstacles to communication efforts led by school administrators. This could involve issues related to technological infrastructure, communication tools, or organizational changes affecting the flow of information.

Participant 12's statement, "Unclear communication, which can lead to concern about findings for the program department," underscores the detrimental effects of unclear communication. It suggests that ambiguous or insufficient communication from leadership can lead to confusion and concern, particularly within specific departments or programs.

Moreover, participant 1 highlights the impact of implementing new policies or strategies that are unfamiliar to members of the institution. This can exacerbate communication challenges, as unfamiliarity with new initiatives may lead to misunderstandings or resistance among staff members.

This theme draws attention to the obstacles encountered in maintaining effective communication during leadership transitions and emphasizes the importance of addressing these challenges for a successful and well-managed transition process. The theme highlights the need for organizations to proactively address communication challenges during leadership transitions, ensuring that information flows smoothly across all levels of the institution.

Table 3. Opportunities that arise during the leadership transition period in terms of effectively managing and supervising the ICCBI operations

Major Themes	Excerpts
Clear Expectations and Communication	"Stablishing clear expectation, offering a safe space and share suggestion or concerns." (P1)
Continuous Professional Development	"A lot of opportunities happen and given in the community. E.g., We as educators are challenged by the administration to experience or to have a lot of trainings, seminars, even project or study, research making etc." (P3)
Equality and Fair Treatment	"Yes, it is more open. Everyone has their privilege to speak up what they want to say." (P4)

Effective Institutional Management	"Yes, a lot of opportunities and positive changes came out as the new leadership wanted to create a positive working environment." (P14)
Creation of New Initiatives	"As the office became more approachable, new initiatives were started, such as the establishment of the research office." (P10)
Transformational Leadership	"The transformational leadership can influence employees' learning experiences by focusing on helping them absorb proactive learning." (P16)

Table 3. shows the opportunities that arise during the leadership transition period in terms of effectively managing and supervising the ICCBI operations. There are six (6) major themes namely:

1. Clear Expectations and Communication
2. Continuous Professional Development
3. Equality and Fair Treatment
4. Effective Institutional Management
5. Creation of New Initiatives
6. Transformational Leadership

Clear Expectations and Communication

This theme emphasizes the fundamental importance of transparent communication and well-defined objectives during leadership transitions at ICCBI. This underscores the need for leaders to establish clear expectations and maintain open communication channels to ensure a smooth transition process. It highlights the pivotal role of transparent communication in mitigating uncertainties, fostering a shared understanding of organizational goals, and promoting a cohesive environment.

Participant 1 emphasizes the significance of establishing clear expectations, providing a safe space for discussion, and encouraging the sharing of suggestions or concerns. This suggests that transparent communication fosters an environment of trust and openness where individuals feel empowered to voice their opinions and contribute to decision-making processes.

By prioritizing clarity and effective communication, leaders of ICCBI can enhance the overall effectiveness of the transition, minimize potential challenges, and create a foundation for collaborative success within the organizational framework. In addition, this guides team members, minimizes confusion, and promotes alignment towards common goals.

Continuous Professional Development

During the leadership transition period at ICCBI, there are significant opportunities for effectively managing and supervising the institution's operations. This critical phase allows for strategic changes, improved communication, and the implementation of innovative policies, fostering a positive impact on the overall management and supervision of ICCBI. The transition period provides a unique window to assess current practices, identify areas for improvement, and implement changes that align with the institution's mission and vision.

Participant 3 highlights the various opportunities provided by the administration, challenging educators to participate in training, seminars, projects, studies, research, and more. This suggests that the leadership transition period is seen as a chance to foster continuous professional development, offering avenues for individuals to expand their expertise and contribute effectively to their roles.

This theme underscores the importance of an organizational culture that prioritizes ongoing learning and development, recognizing it as a valuable opportunity during leadership transitions. Leveraging this period effectively can lead to enhanced operational efficiency, employee engagement, and the establishment of a solid foundation for future success.

Equality and fair treatment

The theme emphasizes the opportunities available during the leadership transition period to foster a workplace culture that prioritizes inclusivity and equitable treatment for all employees. It underscores the significance of promoting fairness, eliminating biases, and establishing environments where every individual feels valued and empowered, regardless of their background or identity. This theme highlights the potential for leaders to drive positive cultural shifts, address systemic inequalities, and create a more supportive and inclusive work environment during times of leadership transition.

Participant 4 emphasizes the openness and inclusivity observed during the transition, where everyone feels empowered to express themselves freely. This suggests that the leadership transition period offers an opportunity to foster an environment where diverse perspectives are welcomed and respected, contributing to a culture of equality and fairness.

Effective institutional management

The theme of "Effective Institutional Management" encapsulates the importance of adept administration, strategic leadership, and proficient governance within organizations. These opportunities play a crucial role in shaping the trajectory of the institution and contribute to its effective management and supervision. The subsequent themes shed light on specific areas where positive transformations and advancements can occur during the leadership transition period, fostering improved operations within ICCBI.

Participant 14 emphasizes the positive changes and opportunities that emerged during the leadership transition, indicating a commitment to creating a positive working environment. This suggests that effective institutional management is an opportunity that arises during the leadership transition period, where new leadership can bring about positive changes and implement strategic initiatives to enhance the overall functioning of the institution.

Creation of New Initiatives

The fifth theme highlights a proactive approach to leadership during the transition period at ICCBI. This major theme centers on the development and implementation of innovative projects or endeavors. The focus is on fostering a culture that encourages creativity, exploration, and the generation of fresh ideas to propel growth, drive change, and address emerging challenges or opportunities.

Participant 10 said, "As the office became more approachable, new initiatives were started, such as the establishment of the research office," which supports the idea that a shift in leadership approach has facilitated the initiation of new projects. This suggests that the leadership transition period is seen as an opportunity to introduce innovative initiatives, contributing to the overall growth and development of ICCBI.

Transformational Leadership

The sixth theme signifies a crucial opportunity during the leadership transition period at ICCBI. This unique opportunity holds significant potential for effectively managing and supervising ICCBI operations. It emphasizes the profound impact and effectiveness of leveraging this transitional phase to foster meaningful change, inspire innovation, and empower individuals and the organization to reach their fullest potential. This theme underscores the positive aspects inherent in leadership transitions, encouraging a proactive approach to harnessing opportunities for organizational growth, development, and overall enhancement in operations at ICCBI.

Participant 16 supports this theme by stating, "Transformational leadership can influence employees' learning experiences by focusing on helping them absorb proactive learning." This suggests that adopting a transformational leadership style can positively impact the learning experiences of employees, aligning with the broader goal of organizational effectiveness.

Table 4. Impact of the leadership transitions on the institution’s mission, vision, and commitment to student success and employees' welfare at ICCBI

Major Themes	Excerpts
<p>Continuity in Vision/Mission and Commitment</p>	<p>"Ever since the change occurred in administration, there has been a continuous commitment to the implementation and welfare of the school’s vision/mission and employees." (P2)</p> <p>"Leadership transition often brings new perspective and priorities to an institution. Successful leadership transition involved careful planning and clear understanding in an organization or institution." (P9)</p> <p>"The administration provides direction and vision, motivates and inspires others to achieve the organization's goals and helps to create an environment conducive to success by promoting communication and collaboration among employees." (P5)</p>
<p>Leadership's Influence on Institution Culture</p>	<p>"What we are what we set, if the leader is a good model this has a good influence on all the staffs, employees, and students." (P3)</p> <p>"I believed that the leadership transition has influenced them positively, emphasizing solidarity and mutual support among staff." (P1)</p>
<p>Focus on Employee Training</p>	<p>"More training was given to the students and employees." (P10)</p> <p>"I think the previous and current admin share the same goal towards the institution's interest and student welfare." (P10)</p>
<p>Alignment of Current Administration with Mission</p>	<p>"I believed that the current administrator's path is towards achieving and realizing its mission and its stakeholders." (P14)</p>

Table 4. highlights the impact of the leadership transitions on the institution’s mission, vision, and commitment to student success and employees' welfare at ICCBI. There are four (4) major themes namely:

1. Continuity in Vision/Mission and Commitment
2. Leadership's Influence on Institution Culture
3. Focus on Employee Training
4. Alignment of Current Administration with Mission

Continuity in Vision, Mission, and Commitment

The first theme underscores the importance of maintaining organizational resilience and success amid leadership transitions at ICCBI. This foundational principle embodies an unwavering dedication to the enduring vision and mission of the institution, serving as a guiding light amidst changing landscapes and evolving challenges.

Participant 2 emphasizes the continuous commitment to the implementation and welfare of the school’s vision, mission, and employees, highlighting that despite the change in administration, the core values and objectives remain steadfast. This sentiment is echoed by Participant 9, who acknowledges that successful leadership transition involves careful planning and a clear understanding of the organization or institution.

Furthermore, Participant 5 highlights the role of the administration in providing direction and vision, motivating and inspiring others to achieve organizational goals, and creating an environment conducive to success through effective communication and collaboration among employees.

Leadership's Influence on Institutional Culture

The second theme focuses on the transformative power of effective leadership in shaping and nurturing a vibrant organizational culture at ICCBI. This major theme highlights the profound impact leaders have on setting the

tone, values, and norms within the institution, influencing behaviors, and fostering an environment conducive to innovation, collaboration, and excellence.

Participant 3 aptly expresses the essence of this theme, stating, "What we are is what we set; if the leader is a good model, this has a good influence on all the staff, employees, and students." This insight emphasizes the direct correlation between leadership practices and the overall culture of the institution. Additionally, Participant 1 supports this perspective by noting that the leadership transition has positively influenced ICCBI, emphasizing solidarity and mutual support among the staff.

Focus on Employee Training

The next theme emphasizes the strategic investment in continuous learning and development as a fundamental driver of organizational growth and resilience at ICCBI. This theme recognizes that a skilled and empowered workforce is crucial for success in a rapidly evolving landscape.

The statement of Participant 10—"more training was given to the students and employees"—reinforces the commitment to enhancing the skills and knowledge of both students and staff. This aligns with the findings of a comprehensive study by Noe et al. (2019), emphasizing the importance of fair and transparent hiring processes, providing training and development opportunities, and fostering a positive work culture to encourage employee engagement and productivity.

Furthermore, the support provided by Participant 10, who stated, "I think the previous and current administrators share the same goal towards the institution's interest and student welfare," indicates continuity in the commitment to employee training, linking it to the broader goals of the institution.

Alignment of Current Administration with Mission

The last theme highlights the critical importance of ensuring that administrative strategies, policies, and decisions are in harmony with the overarching mission and vision of an organization. This theme emphasizes the imperative for the current administration at ICCBI to not only understand but actively uphold the core ethos and objectives of the institution.

The statement *from* Participant 14, "I believed that the current administrator's path is towards achieving and realizing its mission and its stakeholders," provides support for the theme. It indicates a belief in the alignment of the current administration's actions with the institution's mission and commitment to stakeholders.

This theme emphasizes the significance of a cohesive and synchronized approach where the administrative direction is intricately linked with the broader mission and values of ICCBI. It reflects a commitment to preserving the institutional identity and fulfilling the responsibilities towards all stakeholders.

Table 5. Ways to address the challenges of transitions effectively to maintain a positive work environment and enhance organizational effectiveness

Major Themes	Excerpts
Transparency and Communication	"Transparency would rarely help in achieving challenges effectively." (P1) "Clear communication involvement of stakeholders, long-term planning, and assessment." (P9) "Transparency, open communication from the employee to the administrator." (P13)
Employee Involvement and Support	"Be responsible and dedicated in service." (P4) "Remain positive and supportive." (P5)

	<p>"All employees must act professionally." (P15)</p> <p>"Unity and continuous maintenance of a good organization." (P16)</p>
Strategic Planning and Goal Setting	<p>"Establishing clear, specific, and measurable goals and objectives in the organization." (P10)</p> <p>"Administrator continues their goals and on how to improve the institution." (P16)</p> <p>"Cultivate a culture that encourages collaboration, innovation, and a commitment to excellence." (P15)</p> <p>"Early planning, clear communication involving key stakeholders, and orientation." (P9)</p> <p>"Administration needs to know what they are needed for by the employees and students." (P13)</p>
Maintaining Positive Work Environment	<p>"Transparency, conduct of meetings, and team buildings." (P1)</p> <p>"By understanding the needs of employees." (P3)</p> <p>"Communicate effectively and transparently, involve employees in the change process, provide training support." (P5)</p> <p>"Combination of strategic planning, effective communication, and commitment to employees." (P9)</p> <p>"Cultivate a culture that encourages collaboration, innovation, and a commitment to excellence." (P10)</p>
Faculty and Staff Involvement	<p>"Faculty and staff are crucial in the success of an institution, they implement and carry out the mission." (P1)</p> <p>"Faculty and staff should help the administration by doing the work well." (P3)</p> <p>"Their commitment and dedication are essential to maintaining stability during the transition." (P9)</p> <p>"They must be open to possible change in the administration and must cope with this change." (P12)</p> <p>"Helping and supporting the administration for efficient management." (P16)</p>

Table 5. shows ways to address the challenges of transitions in administrations effectively to maintain a positive work environment and enhance organizational effectiveness. There are five (5) major themes identified, namely:

1. Transparency and Communication
2. Employee Involvement and Support
3. Strategic Planning and Goal Setting
4. Maintaining a Positive Work Environment
5. Faculty and Staff Involvement

Transparency and communication

The first theme is pivotal in addressing the challenges of transitions effectively to maintain a positive work environment and enhance organizational effectiveness. This theme underscores the crucial role of open, honest communication and transparent practices as the foundation for fostering trust, cohesion, and synergy within an organization.

The statement from Participant 1, "Transparency would rarely help in achieving challenges effectively," highlights the acknowledgment of transparency as a key element in overcoming challenges. Participant 9 supports this by emphasizing "clear communication, involvement of stakeholders, long-term planning, and assessment," indicating the multifaceted nature of effective communication in navigating transitions. Furthermore, Participant 13 emphasizes "transparency and open communication from the employee to the administrator," underscoring the importance of transparency at all levels of the organizational hierarchy.

Employee Involvement and Support

This theme is pivotal for effectively tackling the challenges associated with transitions and fostering a positive work environment to enhance organizational effectiveness in ICCBI. It underscores the substantial impact of empowering and nurturing the workforce, identifying it as a key element in maintaining organizational vitality during periods of change. Emphasizing the importance of employee empowerment and support, this theme becomes instrumental in creating a resilient and adaptable workforce that contributes positively to the organization's overall health and effectiveness amid transitional phases.

Participant 4 said, "Be responsible and dedicated in service," emphasizing the importance of employee commitment and dedication during transitions. Participants 5 and 15 support this by encouraging a positive and supportive attitude among employees, contributing to a collaborative and constructive work environment. Moreover, Participant 16 emphasizes "unity and continuous maintenance of a good organization," highlighting the collective effort required from employees to maintain a cohesive and positive organizational culture.

Strategic Planning and Goal Setting

This theme arises as a fundamental aspect of effectively addressing the challenges posed by transitions and sustaining organizational effectiveness in ICCBI. It underscores the importance of deliberate planning and establishing clear objectives to navigate through periods of change and uncertainty successfully. By focusing on strategic planning and goal-setting, this becomes instrumental in guiding ICCBI through the complexities of transition, ensuring a cohesive and purposeful approach to managing change and maintaining operational efficiency.

Participant 10 emphasizes the importance of establishing clear, specific, and measurable goals within the organization. This sentiment is echoed by Participant 16, who notes the administrator's commitment to continuing goals and improving the institution. Additionally, Participant 15 underscores the need to cultivate a culture that encourages collaboration, innovation, and excellence, which aligns with the strategic planning process. Similarly, Participant 9 emphasizes the importance of early planning, clear communication involving key stakeholders, and orientation to facilitate successful goal setting and strategic decision-making.

Strategic Planning and Goal Setting highlights the proactive approach organizations take in charting their course amidst transitions. Through establishing clear objectives and fostering a culture of collaboration and excellence, organizations can effectively navigate change and enhance overall organizational effectiveness.

Maintaining a Positive Work Environment

The next theme emerges as a crucial aspect of effectively addressing the challenges of transitions and enhancing organizational effectiveness. This theme underscores the profound impact of fostering a workplace culture that prioritizes well-being, inclusivity, and positivity.

Participant 1 highlights the importance of transparency, the conduct of meetings, and team-building activities in contributing to a positive work environment. This emphasizes the role of open communication, collaboration, and team-building initiatives in fostering a supportive workplace culture.

Moreover, Participant 5 emphasizes the need for effective and transparent communication, involving employees in the change process, and providing training support. This aligns with the broader theme, emphasizing the significance of communication and involvement in creating a positive and adaptive work environment.

Participant 9 further supports this theme by emphasizing the combination of strategic planning, effective communication, and commitment to employees. This underscores the holistic approach organizations take to maintain a positive workplace by integrating strategic planning, clear communication, and a genuine commitment to employee well-being.

In essence, maintaining a positive work environment highlights the essential elements, including communication, teamwork, and strategic planning, that contribute to creating a workplace culture conducive to well-being, inclusivity, and organizational excellence.

Faculty and staff involvement

The last theme highlights the pivotal role and transformative impact of actively engaging and empowering faculty and staff as central stakeholders in the organizational journey. This theme underscores a concerted effort to recognize and leverage the wealth of knowledge, expertise, and dedication that faculty and staff members bring to the organizational context.

Participant 9 emphasizes the crucial role of faculty and staff in the success of an institution, highlighting their role in implementing and carrying out the mission. This statement underscores the integral role faculty and staff play in the execution of organizational goals and objectives.

Additionally, Participant 3 emphasizes that faculty and staff should contribute to the administration by performing their roles effectively. This speaks to the collaborative approach where every member of the organization, including faculty and staff, actively contributes to the collective success.

Furthermore, Participant 9 reinforces the importance of the commitment and dedication of faculty and staff, describing them as essential to maintaining stability during the transition. This recognition underscores the value of their contributions in fostering stability and continuity amid organizational changes.

This theme highlights the organizational commitment to recognizing, valuing, and actively involving faculty and staff, acknowledging their crucial role in shaping the organizational landscape, and ensuring success during periods of transition.

Table 5. Leadership Transition and Organizational Enhancement Strategic Plan

Area	Strategy	Objectives	Persons Involved	Timeline	Budget
Leadership Dynamics	Implement inclusive decision-making processes	- Enhance collaborative decision-making	School Administrators, Department Heads	1-2 months	TBD
	Promote employee growth and well-being	- Develop professional development programs for staff	HR Department, Employee Support Team	3-6 months	TBD
	Strengthen communication and collaboration channels	- Establish regular communication forums and collaboration platforms	Communication Department, Team Leaders	1-3 months	TBD
	Ensure equality and inclusion in leadership practices	- Conduct diversity and inclusion training programs for leaders	Diversity and Inclusion Committee	2-4 months	TBD
Management and Supervision	Address resistance to new policies and unclear communication	- Conduct training on policy implementation and improve communication channels	Change Management Team, Communication Department	2-4 months	TBD
	Navigate technology and communication challenges	- Invest in technology upgrades and provide training on new communication tools	IT Department, Communication Department	3-6 months	TBD
	Seize opportunities like clear communication and continuous professional development	- Develop and implement clear communication strategies - Establish ongoing professional development programs	HR Department, Training and Development Team	1-3 months	TBD
	Leverage transformational leadership	- Provide leadership training programs and mentorship for transformational leadership	Leadership Development Team	4-6 months	TBD
Mission and Vision Alignment	Ensure continuity in the institution's mission, vision, and commitment	- Align new leadership with core values and goals - Establish regular reviews of mission and vision statements	School Administrators, Mission and Vision Committee	2-4 months	TBD
	Focus on employee training and well-being	- Develop and implement employee training programs - Enhance employee support programs	HR Department, Employee Support Team	3-6 months	TBD
Addressing Challenges Effectively	Promote transparency and communication	- Establish transparent communication channels and regular updates on challenges	Communication Department, Leadership Team	1-3 months	TBD
	Encourage employee involvement and support	- Establish feedback mechanisms and employee support programs	Employee Engagement Committee	2-4 months	TBD
	Implement strategic planning and goal setting	- Develop strategic plans aligned with organizational goals - Set clear and measurable objectives	Strategic Planning Team, Department Heads	3-6 months	TBD
Maintaining Positive Work Environment	Cultivate a positive work environment	- Promote team-building activities and initiatives for a positive workplace culture	HR Department, Team Leaders	1-3 months	TBD
	Enhance organizational effectiveness	- Implement efficiency measures and assess organizational processes for improvements	Efficiency Improvement Team	4-6 months	TBD

Leadership Transition and Organizational Enhancement Strategic Plan

The proposed plan, known as the "Leadership Transition and Organizational Enhancement Strategic Plan" (LT-OE Strategic Plan), is a comprehensive framework designed to address the complex challenges and opportunities inherent in the leadership transition at Immaculate Conception College of Balayan Inc. (ICCB). This strategic plan is specifically tailored to meet the unique needs of ICCBI during this transitional phase.

The LT-OE Strategic Plan centers around four key focus areas: Leadership Dynamics, Management and Supervision, Mission, Vision, and Commitment alignment, and Work Environment and Organizational Effectiveness. By concentrating on these critical aspects, the plan aims to create a robust foundation for a successful leadership transition.

Several key strategies have been identified within the plan, including promoting inclusive decision-making processes, prioritizing the growth and well-being of employees, fostering improved communication and collaboration, and ensuring transparency in organizational processes. These strategies are carefully selected to align with the overall objectives of the plan.

The plan sets specific objectives, including facilitating a smooth transition, preserving a positive work environment, aligning the institution's mission with the new leadership, and enhancing overall organizational effectiveness. By delineating these objectives, the plan provides a clear roadmap for achieving success during the transition period.

Key stakeholders involved in the implementation of the LT-OE Strategic Plan include the School Administrator, Human Resources Department, Communication Department, and a dedicated Strategic Planning Team. Their collaboration and coordination are essential to ensure the effective execution of the plan.

The timeline for the plan spans several months, allowing for a strategic allocation of budget resources. This includes provisions for training and development programs, communication tools, and the potential engagement of strategic planning consultants. This financial allocation underscores the commitment to providing the necessary resources for a successful transition.

The LT-OE Strategic Plan is a comprehensive guide that aims to steer ICCBI through a successful leadership transition. By emphasizing collaboration, transparency, and strategic initiatives, the plan positions the institution for sustained success and growth in the long term.

Conclusions

The analysis of the collected data highlights the multifaceted impact of leadership transitions within Immaculate Conception College of Balayan Inc. (ICCB). The transition of leadership significantly influences overall dynamics, affecting various aspects such as the inclusive decision-making process, employee growth and well-being, communication and collaboration, compensation, leadership styles, equality, and inclusion. This underscores the pivotal role of leadership in shaping the success and trajectory of the institution.

Challenges arising during the leadership transition, including resistance to new policies, unclear communication, attachment to previous leaders, and technology challenges, emphasize the complexity of this period. Successful navigation of these challenges requires collaborative efforts from both incoming and outgoing leadership, fostering continuity, stability, and effective management and supervision.

Opportunities emerging from leadership transitions present a unique chance for positive change, fresh ideas, improved processes, and a renewed focus on institutional goals. Organizations can capitalize on these opportunities to foster a positive and dynamic work environment, empowering teams to adapt, collaborate, and thrive under new leadership.

The impact of leadership transitions on ICCBI's mission, vision, commitment to student success, and employees' welfare underscores the importance of aligning new leadership with core values. This alignment is crucial for maintaining continuity, fostering a positive institutional culture, and ensuring ongoing commitment to the welfare of students and employees.

Addressing challenges effectively through transparency, communication, employee involvement and support, strategic planning, maintaining a positive work environment, and faculty and staff involvement becomes paramount. These strategies are essential for fostering a positive workplace culture and maximizing organizational effectiveness during times of change.

The successful management of leadership transitions involves recognizing and addressing challenges, seizing opportunities, and ensuring alignment with the institution's core values. By doing so, ICCBI can navigate transitions effectively, foster a positive work environment, and enhance organizational effectiveness for sustained success.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, several recommendations can be made to address the challenges and capitalize on the opportunities presented by leadership transitions within educational institutions:

For school administrators, it is advisable to prioritize continuous leadership training programs. These programs should focus on enhancing decision-making, communication, and collaboration skills among administrators to ensure a smooth transition and foster effective overall leadership dynamics. Additionally, transparent communication with staff should be prioritized. Open and honest communication channels can help address challenges, maintain morale, and cultivate a positive work environment during periods of transition. Administrators should also implement initiatives aimed at enhancing employee well-being. Recognizing and acknowledging the contributions of staff during transitions and promptly addressing their concerns can help maintain stability and foster a supportive work environment.

For other schools, the recommendation is to study and benchmark best practices from successful leadership transitions in similar institutions. Establishing a network for collaboration and information-sharing among schools undergoing or anticipating leadership transitions can provide valuable insights and strategies for effective management. By learning from the experiences of others, schools can better navigate the challenges associated with leadership changes and ensure continuity in operations.

School employees are encouraged to participate in adaptability training programs to navigate changes effectively during leadership transitions. These programs can help employees develop the skills and resilience needed to thrive in dynamic environments. Additionally, advocating for the establishment of a feedback mechanism allows employees to express concerns and suggestions, ensuring their voices are heard and considered during transitions. By actively engaging in the transition process, employees can contribute to a smoother transition and help maintain productivity and morale.

For future HR professionals, incorporating transition management training into HR programs is crucial. Equipping HR professionals with the necessary skills and knowledge to effectively manage leadership changes can mitigate potential disruptions and ensure continuity in operations. Developing robust employee support systems, including counseling services, is also essential. Addressing the emotional and professional needs of staff during transitions can help alleviate stress and anxiety, promote a positive work environment, and enhance overall employee well-being.

Finally, for future researchers, conducting in-depth case studies similar to this research is recommended. Continually contributing to the knowledge base on leadership transitions provides valuable insights for future decision-makers. Longitudinal studies tracking the long-term effects of leadership transitions on institutions and employees can offer a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon. Exploring cross-industry comparisons can also provide

insights into how leadership transitions in educational institutions compare with those in other sectors, contributing to a broader understanding of effective transition management strategies.

References

- Bartsch, V., Ebers, M., & Maurer, I. (2013). Learning in project-based organizations: The role of project teams' social capital for overcoming barriers to learning. *International Journal of Project Management*, *31*(2), 239–251. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijproman.2012.06.009>
- Basilio, M. (2021). Instructional supervision and assessment in the 21st-century and beyond. *IMRaD Journal*, *4*(2619–7820). <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED629212.pdf>
- Daft, R. L., & Lane, P. G. (2001). *The leadership experience*. <https://ci.nii.ac.jp/ncid/BB01901452>
- Dale, S. (2014). Gamification. *Business Information Review*, *31*(2), 82–90. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0266382114538350>
- Eisenbeis, J., Mahler, T., Lopez, P. R., & Zwick, T. (2018). CHANNEL ESTIMATION METHOD FOR SUBARRAY BASED HYBRID BEAMFORMING SYSTEMS EMPLOYING SPARSE ARRAYS. *Progress in Electromagnetics Research C*, *87*, 25–38. <https://doi.org/10.2528/pierc18062506>
- Faggella-Luby, M. N., & Engel, M. (n.d.). *Why inclusion isn't coming, it is already here: Catholic schools and inclusive special education*. Digital Commons at Loyola Marymount University and Loyola Law School. <https://digitalcommons.lmu.edu/ce/vol23/iss2/4/>
- Herawaty, Y., Hartono, R., & Ramadhan, H. (2020). Strategic management in improving the quality of education in the midst of the COVID-19 pandemic. *Proceedings of the International Conference on Environmental and Technology of Law, Business and Education on Post Covid 19, ICETLAWBE 2020, 26 September 2020, Bandar Lampung, Indonesia*. <https://doi.org/10.4108/eai.26-9-2020.2302768>
- Howell, T. (2022). Coworking spaces: An overview and research agenda. *Research Policy*, *51*(2), 104447. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2021.104447>
- Ishtiaq, M. (2019). Book Review Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative and Mixed Methods Approaches* (4th ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage. *English Language Teaching*, *12*(5), 40. <https://doi.org/10.5539/elt.v12n5p40>
- Kaul, M., Comstock, M., & Simon, N. S. (2022). Leading from the middle: How principals rely on district guidance and organizational conditions in times of crisis. *AERA Open*, *8*, 23328584221077303. <https://doi.org/10.1177/23328584221077303>
- Madden, A., & Kevin. (2020, April 4). *Latest article*. The Word Counter. <https://thewordcounter.com/meaning-of-trajectory/>
- Mangarin, J. (2024). Threats, opportunities, weaknesses, and strengths of the school management strategies used by the Augustinian Recollect (AR) schools. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10595221>
- Parlee, S. D., Simon, B., Scheller, E. L., Alejandro, E. U., Learman, B. S., Krishnan, V., Bernal-Mizrachi, E., & MacDougald, O. A. (2014). Administration of saccharin to neonatal mice influences body composition of adult males and reduces body weight of females. *Endocrinology*, *155*(4), 1313–1326. <https://doi.org/10.1210/en.2013-1995>
- Rob, V. (n.d.). *Noe-et-Al.-2019-Chapter-1*. Scribd. <https://www.scribd.com/document/495809485/Noe-et-al-2019-Chapter-1>

Stoehr, F., Müller, L., Brady, A. P., Trilla, A., Mähringer-Kunz, A., Hähn, F., Düber, C., Becker, N., Wörns, M., Chapiro, J., Hinrichs, J. B., Akata, D., Ellmann, S., Huisman, M., Koff, D., Brinkmann, S., Bamberg, F., Zimmermann, O., Traikova, N., . . . Kloeckner, R. (2021). How COVID-19 kick-started online learning in medical education—The DigiMed study. *PLOS ONE*, *16*(9), e0257394. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0257394>

Strategic Planning for Public and Nonprofit Organizations: A Guide to Strengthening and Sustaining Organizational Achievement, 5th edition. (2017, December 15). Wiley.com. <https://www.wiley.com/en-gb/Strategic+Planning+for+Public+and+Nonprofit+Organizations%3A+A+Guide+to+Strengthening+and+Sustaining+Organizational+Achievement%2C+5th+Edition-p-9781119071600>